

A PROPOSAL OF FE MODELING OF UNIDIRECTIONAL COMPOSITE CONSIDERING UNCERTAIN MICRO STRUCTURE

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1 Introduction

This paper describes about FE modeling method for micro structure of unidirectional composite to estimate the strengths of fibrous composites considering uncertain micro structure. The goal of this study is to estimate the dispersion of fiber bundle's strength. Since new constituent materials such as thermoplastic resin have been developing, the estimation method of the strength from the point of micro scale is critical for the safety and reliability of composite structures.

The uncertainty of micro structure comes from the randomness of fiber arrangement, the effect on mechanical behaviors such as stress distributions or strength have been already discussed in several studies [1][2][3]. In our previous studies [4], the effect of random arrangement of filaments and the residual thermal stresses on the transverse strength was estimated with FE model of UD composite shown in Fig.1. FE model with filaments arranged hexagonally was also generated for the comparison. In the study, numerical results showed good agreement with experimental results, which indicate the importance of considering the random arrangement of filaments for the strength estimation and validity of the numerical method. However, additional modification of the method will be necessary because the computational time and memory requirement were huge.

Fig.1. FE models in previous study [4]

To solve the problem of computational costs, we propose the estimation method of strength by simplified FE model of UD composite. The dispersion of strength is estimated by using the numerical result of several FE models. The procedure of the method and numerical results are described.

2 Proposed method

2.1 Oblique unit cell model

The important factors of micro model (UD composite) are interfacial behavior between filament and resin, residual thermal stress and randomness of fiber arrangements. Considering these factors, FE models of UD composite with 50 filaments arranged randomly (random model) were generated in our previous study [4]. Interfacial behaviors were simulated by interfacial elements inserted between filaments and resin.

Parameters

FE models ($V_f=50\%$)

Fig.2. Oblique unit cell models

In order to reduce the computational cost for FE analysis, random arrangement of filaments is needed to be simulated with small number of filaments. Therefore, FE models with 2 filaments in a unit cell shown in Fig.2 are generated, which are called as Oblique Unit Cell (OUC) model. OUC model is a rotated rectangle unit cell. This is for loading oblique direction of unit cell, which enables θ arbitrarily. The unit cell size is calculated based on the fiber volume fraction and aspect ratio. As the random parameters, distance d and angle θ between 2 filaments and aspect ratio of a unit cell are prepared. Interfacial elements are inserted between resin and filaments. Periodic boundary conditions are applied to OUC model.

2.2 Periodic boundary conditions

In this study, the relative displacement vector is used to consider the periodicity. Fig.3 shows the concept of relative displacement vector. Nodes a and c , nodes b and d are corresponding nodes on the surface of unit cell. Node e is inside the unit cell. In this case, relations between displacements at nodes a , b and at nodes c , d are expressed by Eq. 1 and Eq. 2.

Fig.3. Deformation of periodic surface

$$\mathbf{d}_c = \mathbf{d}_a + \mathbf{d}_\delta \quad (1)$$

$$\mathbf{d}_d = \mathbf{d}_b + \mathbf{d}_\delta \quad (2)$$

where, \mathbf{d}_δ is relative displacement vector. As the nodes a and b in Eq.1 and 2, nodes referred from other nodes are called master node, otherwise, nodes referring other node are called slave node. Eq. 3 shows stiffness equation without periodic boundary condition. Then, Eq. 3 is transformed to Eq. 4 from Eq. 1 and Eq. 2. Furthermore the elements of column c are moved to column a and δ based on the periodicity and Eq. 4 is transformed to Eq.5. In the same procedure, column d , row c and d are moved, too. Finally stiffness equation becomes as shown in Eq.6. The rows and columns concerned with slave nodes in stiffness matrix are removed and new row and column concerned with periodicity are added. By the stiffness equation, FE analysis considering periodicity can be carried out if the relative displacement vectors are determined properly.

$$\begin{Bmatrix} \mathbf{f}_a \\ \mathbf{f}_b \\ \mathbf{f}_c \\ \mathbf{f}_d \\ \mathbf{f}_e \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{k}_{aa} & \mathbf{k}_{ab} & \mathbf{k}_{ac} & \mathbf{k}_{ad} & \mathbf{k}_{ae} \\ \mathbf{k}_{ba} & \mathbf{k}_{bb} & \mathbf{k}_{bc} & \mathbf{k}_{bd} & \mathbf{k}_{be} \\ \mathbf{k}_{ca} & \mathbf{k}_{cb} & \mathbf{k}_{cc} & \mathbf{k}_{cd} & \mathbf{k}_{ce} \\ \mathbf{k}_{da} & \mathbf{k}_{db} & \mathbf{k}_{dc} & \mathbf{k}_{dd} & \mathbf{k}_{de} \\ \mathbf{k}_{ea} & \mathbf{k}_{eb} & \mathbf{k}_{ec} & \mathbf{k}_{ed} & \mathbf{k}_{ee} \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \mathbf{d}_a \\ \mathbf{d}_b \\ \mathbf{d}_c \\ \mathbf{d}_d \\ \mathbf{d}_e \end{Bmatrix} \quad (3)$$

$$\begin{Bmatrix} \mathbf{f}_a \\ \mathbf{f}_b \\ \mathbf{f}_c \\ \mathbf{f}_d \\ \mathbf{f}_e \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{k}_{aa} & \mathbf{k}_{ab} & \mathbf{k}_{ac} & \mathbf{k}_{ad} & \mathbf{k}_{ae} \\ \mathbf{k}_{ba} & \mathbf{k}_{bb} & \mathbf{k}_{bc} & \mathbf{k}_{bd} & \mathbf{k}_{be} \\ \mathbf{k}_{ca} & \mathbf{k}_{cb} & \mathbf{k}_{cc} & \mathbf{k}_{cd} & \mathbf{k}_{ce} \\ \mathbf{k}_{da} & \mathbf{k}_{db} & \mathbf{k}_{dc} & \mathbf{k}_{dd} & \mathbf{k}_{de} \\ \mathbf{k}_{ea} & \mathbf{k}_{eb} & \mathbf{k}_{ec} & \mathbf{k}_{ed} & \mathbf{k}_{ee} \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \mathbf{d}_a \\ \mathbf{d}_b \\ \mathbf{d}_a + \mathbf{d}_\delta \\ \mathbf{d}_b + \mathbf{d}_\delta \\ \mathbf{d}_e \end{Bmatrix} \quad (4)$$

$$\begin{Bmatrix} \mathbf{f}_a \\ \mathbf{f}_b \\ \mathbf{f}_c \\ \mathbf{f}_d \\ \mathbf{f}_e \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{k}_{aa} + \mathbf{k}_{ac} & \mathbf{k}_{ab} & \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{k}_{ad} & \mathbf{k}_{ea} & \mathbf{k}_{ac} \\ \mathbf{k}_{ba} + \mathbf{k}_{bc} & \mathbf{k}_{bb} & \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{k}_{bd} & \mathbf{k}_{eb} & \mathbf{k}_{bc} \\ \mathbf{k}_{ca} + \mathbf{k}_{cc} & \mathbf{k}_{cb} & \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{k}_{cd} & \mathbf{k}_{ec} & \mathbf{k}_{cc} \\ \mathbf{k}_{da} + \mathbf{k}_{dc} & \mathbf{k}_{db} & \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{k}_{dd} & \mathbf{k}_{ed} & \mathbf{k}_{dc} \\ \mathbf{k}_{ea} + \mathbf{k}_{ec} & \mathbf{k}_{eb} & \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{k}_{ed} & \mathbf{k}_{ee} & \mathbf{k}_{ec} \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \mathbf{d}_a \\ \mathbf{d}_b \\ \mathbf{d}_a \\ \mathbf{d}_b + \mathbf{d}_\delta \\ \mathbf{d}_e \\ \mathbf{d}_\delta \end{Bmatrix} \quad (5)$$

$$\begin{Bmatrix} \mathbf{f}_a + \mathbf{f}_c \\ \mathbf{f}_b + \mathbf{f}_d \\ \mathbf{f}_e \\ \mathbf{f}_\delta \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{k}_{aa} + \mathbf{k}_{ac} + \mathbf{k}_{ca} + \mathbf{k}_{cc} & \mathbf{k}_{ab} + \mathbf{k}_{ad} + \mathbf{k}_{cb} + \mathbf{k}_{cd} & \mathbf{k}_{ea} + \mathbf{k}_{ec} & \mathbf{k}_{ac} + \mathbf{k}_{ad} + \mathbf{k}_{cc} + \mathbf{k}_{cd} \\ \mathbf{k}_{ba} + \mathbf{k}_{bc} + \mathbf{k}_{da} + \mathbf{k}_{dc} & \mathbf{k}_{bb} + \mathbf{k}_{bd} + \mathbf{k}_{ab} + \mathbf{k}_{dd} & \mathbf{k}_{eb} + \mathbf{k}_{ed} & \mathbf{k}_{bc} + \mathbf{k}_{bd} + \mathbf{k}_{dc} + \mathbf{k}_{ad} \\ \mathbf{k}_{ea} + \mathbf{k}_{ec} & \mathbf{k}_{eb} + \mathbf{k}_{ed} & \mathbf{k}_{ee} & \mathbf{k}_{ec} + \mathbf{k}_{ea} \\ \mathbf{k}_{ac} + \mathbf{k}_{ad} + \mathbf{k}_{cc} + \mathbf{k}_{cd} & \mathbf{k}_{bc} + \mathbf{k}_{bd} + \mathbf{k}_{dc} + \mathbf{k}_{ad} & \mathbf{k}_{ec} + \mathbf{k}_{ea} & \mathbf{k}_{cc} + \mathbf{k}_{cd} + \mathbf{k}_{dc} + \mathbf{k}_{dd} \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \mathbf{d}_a \\ \mathbf{d}_b \\ \mathbf{d}_e \\ \mathbf{d}_\delta \end{Bmatrix} \quad (6)$$

2.3 Enforced displacement value

There are 3 periodic surfaces to which appropriate displacement should be applied. Fig.4 shows the deformation of OUC model when loading to x direction. In the figure, $\mathbf{d1}$ and $\mathbf{d2}$ are periodic vectors and $\mathbf{d1}_\delta$ and $\mathbf{d2}_\delta$ are displacements added to $\mathbf{d1}$ and $\mathbf{d2}$.

Fig.4. Deformation of a OUC model

$\mathbf{d1}_\delta$ and $\mathbf{d2}_\delta$ when providing strain ε to x direction are expressed by Eq.7 and 8, calculated based on the uniform ratio of area expansion.

$$\mathbf{d1}_\delta = \left(1 + \frac{L_1 \cos(\beta + \theta)}{L_2 \cos(\alpha - \theta)} \right) \frac{\varepsilon L}{2} \quad (7)$$

$$\mathbf{d2}_\delta = \left(1 - \frac{L_1 \cos(\beta + \theta)}{L_2 \cos(\alpha - \theta)} \right) \frac{\varepsilon L}{2} \quad (8)$$

Poisson's effect is also considered when y direction of periodic surface is free. When provide out of plane share load, $\mathbf{d1}_\delta$, $\mathbf{d2}_\delta$ and $\mathbf{d3}_\delta$ which is periodicity in z direction are needed to be calculated. The same method as leading Eq.7 and 8 can be applied to calculate these values.

2.4 FE analysis based on damage mechanics

FE analysis based on damage mechanics is carried out with 100 numbers of OUC models. Fig.5 shows the method of damage development analysis. The detail of the method is described in reference [5]. When the initial failure occurs at this point (A), the modulus of damaged element is reduced. If the neighbor element is broken by the stress concentration due to the release of stress, the

modulus of the neighbor element is also reduced. Finally, if any elements don't fail at this point (B), the analysis is progressed into the next step. And, the same calculation is carried out at the point (C), (D) and (E).

Table 1 shows mechanical properties of polyester resin, interfacial element between filament and resin and glass filament used in the analysis. Except compressive strength, resin and interface have common properties. Hoffman's criterion is applied as damage criterion to consider the difference of tensile and compressive strength.

Fig.5. Damage development analysis method

Table 1 Mechanical properties
(a) Polyester resin and interfacial element

Property	Symbol	Data
Young's modulus[GPa]	E_m	2.614
Shear modulus[GPa]	G_m	972.7
Poisson's ratio	ν_m	0.3866
Coefficient of thermal Expansion[$10^{-6}/^{\circ}\text{C}$]	α_m	150
Tensile strength[MPa]	F_T	80
Shear strength[MPa]	F_s	80
compressive strength[MPa]	F_c	resin : 160 interface : 250

(b) Glass filament

Property	Symbol	Data
Young's modulus[GPa]	E_f	74.75
Shear modulus[GPa]	G_f	28.75
Poisson's ratio	ν_f	0.3
Coefficient of thermal Expansion[$10^{-6}/^{\circ}\text{C}$]	α_f	5
Tensile strength[MPa]	F_f	1857

3 Results of analysis

100 OUC models with the volume fraction of fiber 30,

40, 50, 60 and 70% respectively are generated and FE analyses are carried out. Fig.6 shows stress distributions of x direction in hexagonal model and OUC model with and without residual thermal stress. Filaments are invisible in the figure. The stress in OUC model is higher than hexagonal model for the short distance of filaments and stresses on near $\alpha=180$ degree is high without thermal stresses on the other hand $\alpha=150$ degree is high with thermal stresses for the effect of stress relaxation.

Fig.6. Distribution of x stress

Fig.7 shows reduction of stiffness and Fig.8 shows damage development of OUC model. Black elements are treated as damaged and the stiffness is reduced. As shown in figures, the toughness will be higher with considering thermal stresses, because damage occur and develop in larger strain than the numerical results without thermal stresses.

Fig.7. Reduction of stiffness

Fig.8. Damage developments (x strain=0.55%)

However, the tendency was appeared in case strength without thermal stress is low, the model of distance between 2 filaments is short. In case the distance is long, strength decreases. Therefore, the average of the strengths was lower when considering residual thermal stresses. Fig.9 shows relationship between strength and volume fraction of fiber (V_f) obtained from 100 number of OUC models at each V_f respectively. The distribution is characterized by Weibull's distribution and scatter bar shows 0.01 and 0.99 of cumulative distribution function. For the reason described above, dispersion of strength in micro scale is smaller when residual thermal stresses are considered.

Fig.9. Transverse strength

Strengths and damage developments under share and compressive loads are also able to be estimated by the method. Fig.10 shows examples of the damage developments under compressive and share load.

A PROPOSAL OF FE MODELING OF UNIDIRECTIONAL COMPOSITE CONSIDERING UNCERTAIN MICRO STRUCTURE

Fig.10. Damage developments

Fig.11 shows the strengths in micro scale when out of plane share load and tensile or compressive load are combined. This curve is also led by some kind of damage criterion such as Hoffman's criterion. In case of the unit cells with several filaments, it spends too much computational costs. However, OUC model enables to reduce 0.1% of the computational time compared with the unit cell models with 50 filaments.

Fig.11. Damage envelope

Fig.12. Relationship between number of filaments in a unit cell and strength.

There are relation between the number of filament in a unit cell and distribution of strength that when the number of filaments increases, average of strength

and dispersion decreases as shown in Fig.12. The relation is important to estimate strength at fiber bundle scale based on the result of OUC model. The relation is clearly due to the damage initiation is the weakest part when the number of filaments is large such as the model shown in Fig.1.

4 Estimation of strength at fiber bundle scale

Table 2 is scale and shape parameters of mechanical properties of transverse direction in micro scale obtained from OUC models without considering residual thermal stresses. Two damage modes, which are the damage of interface and resin, is considered because stiffness decreases to about half when interface damaged and when resin damaged, stiffness drops significantly. Dispersions are characterized based on Weibull's distribution.

Table 2 Mechanical properties of transverse direction

(a)Scale parameter

Volume fraction of fiber [%]	30	40	50	60	70
Young's modulus[GPa]	5.06	6.24	8.12	10.6	15.5
Stress[MPa] : interface damaged	34.6	34.3	32.7	33.3	32.5
Strain [%] : resin damaged	0.75	0.69	0.68	0.65	0.53

(b)Shape parameter

Volume fraction of fiber [%]	30	40	50	60	70
Young's modulus	31.0	19.9	15.4	12.3	8.4
Stress: interface damaged	8.61	7.06	7.68	7.61	8.36
Strain: resin damaged	7.2	5.9	4.1	3.5	3.3

Fig.13. FE model of UD

These mechanical properties are applied to FE model shown in Fig.13 which is composed of 100 elements with the properties of OUC, assumes about 50 to 100 filaments in a model. Mechanical properties of elements are determined by random number based on distribution shown in Table 2. The volume fraction (V_f) of elements are determined randomly, aiming the

average V_f is target value.

Fig.14 shows the result of analysis, comparing the result of random model with 50 filaments shown in Fig.1. Both the case with and without thermal stress, the results of proposed model in Fig.9 agreed with the results of random model. Though the strengths of OUC model are about 30MPa, the strengths of UD are smaller. This is because of the dispersion of strength (weak element damaged) and the effect of variance of local volume fraction of fiber.

Fig.14. Result of analysis

By using the proposed method, shear strength and compressive strength might be estimated as well. In the future studies, the dispersion of mechanical properties of UD is applied to meso scale model to carry out multi-scale analysis.

5 Conclusions

- 1) FE analysis of oblique unit cell (OCU) model has been proposed to estimate mechanical properties of unidirectional composite at micro scale.
- 2) Mechanical properties of micro scale are characterized based on Weibull's distribution from 100 number of OUC models.
- 3) From the result of OUC models, mechanical properties at fiber bundle scale can be estimated.

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